

The Critical Success Factors of a Green University: Students' Perspective

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ABSTRACT: Sustainable universities strive to integrate environmentally responsible practices into their academic programs and campus facilities. This study aims to identify the key Critical Success Factors (CSFs) that define a green university. To achieve this target a university with two campuses in Abu Dhabi and Al Ain, United Arab Emirates (UAE), was selected to assess whether it aligns with these criteria from the perspective of its students. A quantitative, cross-sectional survey was conducted among 257 students, from the College of Health Sciences (CHS), focusing on attributes such as environmental education, sustainability knowledge, energy efficiency, waste management, and social benefits. The study revealed 14 factors that significantly influence students' perspectives on how they perceive their university as green. Thus, considering these factors, 76% of the students distinguish their university as a 'green university', particularly focusing on sustainability awareness, sustainability courses integration into the curriculum, the accessibility of educational services, and the availability of facilities for students with disabilities. Eventually, if universities manage to communicate about sustainability efforts and expand resource-saving initiatives, there will be a high potential to have more green universities. These findings contribute to the existing body of knowledge by presenting student-centered insights into the CSFs that influence perceptions of green universities in the UAE context. The study also highlights the significance of integrating sustainability education and inclusive facilities as essential drivers for promoting environmental responsibility within higher education institutions.

Key words: Green University, higher education, sustainability, success factors, student perspectives.

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1. Introduction

Green universities are recognized as educational institutions committed to environmental sustainability within their academic systems. Their central goal is to reduce their ecological footprint by implementing different sustainability practices, including energy efficiency, water conservation, sustainable transportation, waste reduction, and environmental education. In addition to such attempts, green universities adopt social well-being and tolerance to fulfil the needs of all individuals, including those with disabilities.

These institutions foster a broad learning environment, encouraging ecological awareness and sustainable living standards among students. Consequently, green universities play a vital role in supporting those with certain disabilities and developing a sense of belonging among students.

Green universities contribute to boosting social views and fostering tolerance through the establishment of green spaces on campus (Begum et al., 2021; Makuch & Aczel, 2020). Scholars have agreed that these spaces can improve overall student well-being, lower stress levels, and reduce anxiety, thus encouraging greater tolerance and social interaction among students from different cultural and ethnic backgrounds (Ardoin et al., 2020; Atici et al., 2021). Besides, green universities keenly engage in sustainability initiatives such as Earth Day events, community clean-ups, and environmental fairs (Alnaqbi et al., 2024; Ragazzi & Ghidini, 2017). These activities raise awareness of environmental responsibilities and promote the inclusion of students despite their differences (Hassan & Al-Ali, 2024; Wu, 2021). Also, green universities provide essential physical services, infrastructure, and technological support to ensure a safe and rich academic environment for students (Kobori et al., 2015). Such inclusiveness raises respect and acceptance for diversity within the university community (Begum et al., 2021; Ragazzi & Ghidini, 2017).

This study is significant for numerous reasons. Universities shape societal norms and advance sustainability initiatives (Ardoin et al., 2020). Given their widespread presence, green universities significantly contribute to sustainability by promoting environmental awareness and responsible behavior among students (Liobikienė & Minelgaitė, 2018). Previous research has revealed that students at green universities confirmed that their institutions foster active environmental initiatives (Liobikienė & Minelgaitė, 2018). Further, students studying at green universities engage more in sustainability practices, unlike others at non-green universities (Liobikienė & Minelgaitė, 2018). In particular, the UAE has emerged as a leading advocate for sustainable development, making considerable efforts to support green initiatives within its higher education sector (Albattah & Bande, 2023; Jose & Chacko, 2017).

This study aims to analyze the essential components of green universities and evaluate the Critical Success Factors (CSFs) that verify their sustainability from students' perspectives. This research will investigate whether the selected academic institution satisfies green university criteria and emphasize the significance of sustainability from students' perspectives. The findings of this study will highlight insights into how higher education institutions can align their sustainability targets with student expectations to improve the overall sustainability of the higher education sector. The specific objectives of this study are to examine the main sustainability CSFs adopted by the selected University and to evaluate whether students perceive their university as green. Although many universities in the UAE pursue environmental initiatives, there is a lack of empirical studies evaluating their effectiveness (Albattah & Bande, 2023; Jose & Chacko, 2017). Yet, the university selected for this study has a solid academic reputation and commitment to sustainability, making it an ideal choice for this research. The outcomes of this study will provide constructive insights for higher education institutions in the UAE, guiding them in their efforts to improve sustainability and embrace innovative solutions (Albattah & Bande,

2023; Jose & Chacko, 2017). Furthermore, engaging students in discussions about sustainability will raise enthusiasm and boost their participation in making universities more environmentally friendly (Begum et al., 2021; Wu, 2021). Despite growing global interest in higher education sustainability, there remains a gap in explaining how students perceive and evaluate green universities, specifically in the UAE context (Albattah & Bande, 2023; Hassan, A., 2024; Jose & Chacko, 2017). This study aims to fill this gap by offering empirical data on student perspectives about the sustainability efforts of their university, thus contributing to the broader discourse on green universities and their effect on student engagement and institutional development (Ardoin et al., 2020; Ragazzi & Ghidini, 2017). Ultimately, the objectives of this study are: (1) to identify the key Critical Success Factors (CSFs) that define a green university, and (2) to assess, from students' perspectives, whether the selected institution in the UAE aligns with those CSFs.

2. Literature Review

Many universities have understood the importance of promoting sustainability and have redesigned their activities to be performed considering it. The literature indicates that social well-being and tolerance; environmental education and ecology; energy and resource-saving cooperation; and inclusion of sustainability concepts in programs and research are imperative aspects that can transform a traditional university into a green university.

Social well-being and tolerance

Social well-being and tolerance are key elements of green universities since they offer a sustainable environment for learners despite differences (Makuch & Aczel, 2020). Social well-being describes people's physical, emotional, and social health. Tolerance is the capacity of society to accept and integrate groups perceived as different into their midst (Azeiteiro & Davim, 2019; Hawkins, et al., 2023). Green universities address social well-being and tolerance in their programs and handle the concerns of all individuals (including individuals with disabilities) (Clery et al., 2021; Filho, et al., 2016; Fuertes-Camacho et al., 2019). These aspects also cultivate an environment that supports sustainable learning practices, ecological awareness, and social justice (Citing Ardoin et al., 2020; Kobori et al., 2015; Wu, 2021). Green universities also emphasize a healthy physical, emotional, and social atmosphere for all individuals within the learning institutions (Atici et al., 2021; Hassan, 2021d; Kobori et al., 2015). Such an atmosphere enhances students' academic performance and promotes a healthy environment for individuals studying or working at a green university (Hassan, 2020; Makuch & Aczel, 2020). Moreover, social well-being and tolerance in green universities are effective policies and processes that involve vulnerable groups such as disabled individuals and those who are from diverse backgrounds (Hassan et al. 2024; Keis 2020). Keis (2020) has pointed out the importance of creating a positive education and well-being culture for individuals with special educational needs or disabilities. Keis (2020) has encouraged green universities to use eco-friendly designs to ensure healthy and sustainable buildings. In addition, green universities care about social activities that highlight diversity, acceptance, and tolerance (Makuch & Aczel, 2020; Wu, 2021). They focus on details such as positive mental health, availability of exercise areas,

and community involvement in social activities (Alnaqbi et al., 2024; Smith et al., 2017). Another crucial concern is an individual's relationships with peers to develop a healthy learning environment (Alnaqbi et al., 2024; Filho, et al., 2016). Therefore, green universities address social inclusion and equity in their goals (Fuertes-Camacho et al., 2019; Hawkins, et al., 2023).

Environmental education and ecology

Environmental education impacts students' behavior toward the environment at green universities (Begum et al., 2021). Yet, ecological responsibility, education, and ethical challenges exist at these universities (Atici et al., 2021; Wu, 2021). This encourages green universities to conserve resources to improve environmental education and encourage eco-friendly behavior (Ardoin et al., 2020; Kobori et al., 2015). Numerous studies have highlighted the direct relationship between environmental education and eco-friendly behavior (Liobikienė, & Minelgaitė, 2018; Makuch & Aczel, 2020; Smith et al., 2017). Other scholars have found a link between ecological education, eco-friendly behavior, and environmental responsibility (Azeiteiro & Davim, 2019; Begum et al., 2021). Ardoin et al., (2020) have mentioned that Environmental education improves attitudes, values, understanding, and skills needed to create a sustainable learning environment. Further, environmental education plays a vital role in resolving emerging environmental problems (Atici et al., 2021; Clery et al., 2021). For better conservation and environmental quality, it is essential to encourage and support research to enhance the effectiveness of environmental education at green universities (Ardoin et al., 2020; Hassan, 2023a; Kattan & Hassan, 2010). Kobori et al., (2015) have motivated ecology researchers to support conservation programs through addressing challenging environmental issues. Examples of model ecological and conservation issues are macro-ecology, endangered species, and biodiversity (Kobori et al., 2015).

Energy and resource-saving cooperation

Sustainability is a necessity, which has led several universities to move toward being a green university (Hawkins, et al., 2023; Keis, 2020). Here, it is important to understand that green universities conserve energy and resources (Atici et al., 2021; Filho, et al., 2016). Wu (2021) has pointed out that any university could reduce energy consumption and carbon emissions by using energy-efficient tools. In the long term, such a step creates a sustainable environment and reduces energy costs at educational institutions (Wu, 2021). Wu (2021) has added that green universities, that undertake efficient energy conservation measures realize sustainable development goals. The reason is that they act as a reference point for the utilization of resources needed for students or any other affected individuals (Wu, 2021). Ragazzi and Ghidini (2017) have emphasized the importance of using a systematic assessment and ranking of existing environmental impacts, such as the UI Green Metric, to increase universities' awareness about energy and resource-saving measures. Such rankings provide a system that allows green universities to measure their sustainable practices and find effective ways to improve them (Ragazzi & Ghidini, 2017). They also inspire green universities to focus on energy and resource conservation in the existing facilities and measure their progress (Hassan, 2023b; Ragazzi & Ghidini, 2017). It is also crucial to boost leadership and partnerships that support environmental initiatives in

higher education institutions (Alnaqbi et al., 2024). Atici et al. (2021) have stated that cooperation between universities and business partners could improve energy and resource conservation in higher education institutions. Furthermore, it is meaningful to encourage environmental management, competitiveness, collaborations, research, and technological advancements to utilize efficient energy and resource conservation tools and techniques (Atici et al., 2021; Kyrychenko et al., 2021).

The inclusion of sustainability aspects in programs and research

Educational institutions are the basis of learning and knowledge promotion worldwide. Environment, safety, and sustainability are among the most central matters the world is interested in, hence including sustainability educational programs and research is essential for universities (Azeiteiro & Davim, 2019; Filho et al., 2016). This helps them promote ideas such as conserving resources and creating a healthy environment. The integration of sustainability in educational institutions was not considered in many countries worldwide (Azeiteiro & Davim, 2019; Hassan, 2023c). Recently, sustainability promotion has spread nationally and internationally (Fuertes-Camacho et al., 2019). The focus has increased on environmental education (Azeiteiro & Davim, 2019; Fuertes-Camacho et al., 2019). It was agreed that it should be accessible to all individuals, particularly those who teach or conduct research about sustainability (Clery et al., 2021). At the same time, it has become important to provide formal and nonformal training to educators to adopt sustainability in educational programs and research (Azeiteiro & Davim, 2019). Lately, the aspects of sustainability have been incorporated into several courses. This assists in improving consciousness about sustainability and its importance (Clery et al., 2021; Hassan, 2022). In addition, many scholars have agreed that interest and adoption of sustainability have increased in various fields and disciplines (Filho et al., 2016). In turn, when adopted in educational institutions, this enhanced educational quality and improved students' confidence in finding innovative solutions in favor of the environment (Filho et al., 2016). Clery et al. (2021) have pointed out that students' skills are enhanced when integrating sustainability into education. This has led numerous universities to view sustainability as an imperative title to add to the educational programs for various specializations (Clery et al., 2021; Filho et al., 2016). Yet, project-based learning boosts students' understanding of sustainability, such as climate change, biodiversity, renewable energy, and natural resources conservation (Fuertes-Camacho et al., 2019; Hassan, A. 2021a). Project-based learning also enhances teachers' understanding of sustainability applications and challenges (Azeiteiro & Davim, 2019; Fuertes-Camacho et al., 2019).

Accordingly, previous research has focused on the positive impacts of green universities (Citing Ardoin et al., 2020; Keis, 2020). At the same time, some existing literature highlighted many factors that describe sustainable universities (Begum et al., 2021; Fuertes-Camacho et al., 2019). However, this research aims to fill this gap by determining the critical success factors that identify a green university based on the students' perspective.

3. Research Methodology

Quantitative research is an impactful type of research that several authors in the field of sustainability rely on (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). Many scholars have agreed that quantitative research is the best way to predict, identify, and understand sustainability factors and interventions that influence academic institutions, to be considered green institutions (Hair et al., 2019; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019). Numerous articles about green institutions have selected quantitative research to identify the factors necessary to categorize these institutions as green ones (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). Generally, quantitative research is often used to assess the accuracy of assumptions using surveys (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019). Such surveys are sent to a certain audience that has good knowledge and experience about the topic of the study, this increases the credibility of the results and findings (Hair et al., 2019). The survey sent to participants, the collected responses, and the analyzed data determine the adequacy of the study findings (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019). Using numerical data and analysis, quantitative research could effectively be used to examine the main factors leading to green institutions (Hair et al., 2019; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019).

Accordingly, the research setting, duration, and instruments have been selected accurately to explore the CSFs essential to developing a green university. The research was conducted at a university with two campuses in Abu Dhabi and Al Ain, United Arab Emirates. The survey distribution started from the beginning of September 2024 to the end of November 2024. To distribute the questionnaire, social media platforms such as Microsoft Teams and WhatsApp. Further, the target population was the College of Health Science undergraduate students at the selected university. The participants differed in their genders, ages, nationalities, and educational seniority levels. The population was 1,116 individuals, representing the CHS students on both campuses of the selected university. The sample size was calculated to determine the study's sample, considering a 0.5 population variability, 0.95 confidence interval, 5% margin of error, and 20% drop-out rate (Hair et al., 2019). To realize a 95% confidence level that the true value is within 5% of the surveyed value, 286 measurements or more are needed (Hair et al., 2019; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019). Consequently, the study sample size is 286. However, due to time constraints, the sample size was 257 responses. These responses were based on a random sampling technique.

Data was collected using an online survey. The survey was sent to the CHS undergraduate students at the chosen university, via Microsoft and WhatsApp. The questionnaire included twenty questions categorized into two sections: sociodemographic characteristics (age, sex, nationality, seniority level, etc.) and the green university CSFs collected from the literature review such as social well-being, environmental education, and sustainability research. The data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 29. The factor analysis was used to identify the CSFs of a green university. Nevertheless, participation in this study was voluntary, giving full freedom to participants to accept or reject being involved. The required ethical standards were met, considering approval from the selected university's Institutional Review Board (IRB) for data collection. For confidentiality purposes, no identifying information was required from the respondent. The data received from the respondents was considered confidential and

privacy was maintained. The data would not be shared with anyone not involved in the research and measures were formed to protect participants' identities.

4. Results and Discussion

The demographic characteristics of the respondents demonstrate diverse perspectives on sustainability as shown in Table 1. The study sample included 71.60% female and 28.40% male students. This suggests that female students were more engaged or interested in sustainability-related topics. Numerous scholars agree that females express greater environmental concerns and are more active in sustainability initiatives (Meinzen-Dick, et al. 2014). Age distribution showed that most students fell within the 18-20 age group (32.68%), followed by 23-25 years (23.74%), 21-22 years (21.01%), 25 and above (18.29%), and under 18 (4.28%), respectively. This distribution indicates that sustainability awareness and engagement were prevalent across various age groups, with younger students likely being informed about sustainability fundamentals through coursework and other university initiatives (Wiernik, et al., 2013). Older students, specifically those in the 23-25 age range, had more opportunities to engage in sustainability-related coursework, projects, or research, potentially affecting their perceptions of the university's green initiatives (Wiernik, et al., 2013). Regarding the seniority level, it was found that the students' categories were 42.80% seniors (fourth year), 21.79% juniors (third year), 19.07% freshmen (first year), and 16.34% sophomores (second year). The substantial participation of senior students indicates that they might have had greater exposure to university sustainability efforts throughout the years, enabling them to provide informed opinions on the efficacy of these initiatives. On the other hand, freshmen and sophomores were familiarizing themselves with campus sustainability programs, which might have affected their perceptions differently. Most respondents were from the Abu Dhabi campus (93.39%), while a smaller proportion was from the Al Ain campus (6.61%) of the selected university. This imbalance may reflect variations in the campus size, student population, or sustainability initiatives employed at each location. Sustainability efforts were visible or better communicated at the Abu Dhabi campus, leading to a higher response rate. Understanding the differences between campuses helps university administrators tailor their sustainability strategies to ensure that all students, in any location, have equal access to green initiatives and resources (Mian et al., 2020). Concerning nationality, Arab students were the majority at 92.22%, whereas non-Arab students were 7.78%. This demographic composition aligns with the overall student population at the university and implies that sustainability perceptions are shaped mainly within an Arab cultural context. Considering that sustainability values can be affected by cultural and regional factors; it is crucial to consider how these aspects align with worldwide sustainability goals and practices (Adams, et al., 2018). These demographic factors represent a critical context for interpreting students' viewpoints on sustainability. The variety (in gender, age, seniority level, campus location, and nationality) points out the broad reach of sustainability initiatives and the need for effective programs that accommodate all student groups (Fissi et al., 2021). Understanding diversity helps universities select effective sustainability strategies, maximize student engagement, and create a green campus environment (Adams, et al., 2018; Fissi et al., 2021).

Table 1. The study's demographic characteristics

Variable	Percent (%)
Gender	Male: 28.40%
	Female: 71.60%
Age	Under 18: 4.28%
	18-20: 32.68%
	21-22: 21.01%
	23-25: 23.74%
	25 and above: 18.29%
Seniority level	Freshman (First year): 19.07%
	Sophomore (Second year): 16.34%
	Junior (Third year): 21.79%
	Senior (Fourth year): 42.80%
University Campus	Abu Dhabi campus respondents: 93.39%
	Al Ain campus respondents: 6.61%
Nationality	Arab respondents: 92.22%
	Non-Arab respondents: 7.78%

In this study, only CSFs with a value of 0.6 or greater were selected (Hair et al., 2019; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019). The authors state that loadings above 0.6 are strong indicators of a meaningful factor structure in exploratory factor analysis. This threshold ensures that the identified factors reflect students' perceptions of sustainability within their university environment. All fourteen factors in this study met the required threshold, indicating none were rejected, emphasizing their importance in distinguishing a green campus. However, the factor analysis results emphasize key sustainability components that substantially impact students' perceptions of a green university as shown in Table 2. Among the highest-rated factors, student awareness of climate change (0.844) was the most important, pointing out the significance of educating students about environmental issues (Azeiteiro & Davim, 2019; Fuertes-Camacho et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2017). Environmental education in all majors (0.831) and accessible sustainability education (0.826) were also greatly supported, highlighting the need for sustainability to be integrated across diverse academic fields (Alnaqbi et al., 2024; Azeiteiro & Davim, 2019; Begum et al., 2021). Resources for students with disabilities (0.830) and partnerships for resource-saving projects (0.813) were recognized as crucial aspects of collaboration in sustainability efforts (Makuch & Aczel, 2020; Smith et al., 2017; Wu, 2021). Energy efficiency and sustainability (0.789), commitment to green practices (0.764), and collaboration for energy-saving initiatives (0.763) underscore the importance of institutional efforts in advancing an environmentally accountable campus (Adams, et al., 2018; Mian et al., 2020). Other key factors include support for sustainable research (0.744), equal opportunities in sustainability programs (0.739), sustainability information on the website (0.737), and recycling bins availability (0.716), all of which focus on the need for awareness, accessibility, and infrastructure to promote sustainability (Clery et al., 2021; Fuertes-Camacho et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2017; Wu, 2021). Moreover, sustainability through student clubs (0.679) and courses on sustainability (0.682) emphasize the role of student engagement and curriculum design in shaping environmental consciousness (Begum et al., 2021; Clery et al., 2021; Filho, et al., 2016; Fuertes-Camacho et al., 2019). These findings display an inclusive

approach to sustainability, integrating institutional commitment, education, inclusivity, and student participation (Atici et al., 2021; Alnaqbi et al., 2024; Keis, 2020; Kobori et al., 2015; Makuch & Aczel, 2020; Smith et al., 2017).

Table 2. The study factor analysis

No.	Factors	Value	No.	Factors	Value
1	Energy Efficiency and Sustainability	0.789	8	Sustainability through Student Clubs	0.679
2	Resources for Students with Disabilities	0.830	9	Accessible Sustainability Education	0.826
3	Recycling Bins Availability	0.716	10	Equal Opportunities in Sustainability Programs	0.739
4	Sustainability Information on the Website	0.737	11	Student Awareness of Climate Change	0.844
5	Collaboration for Energy-Saving Initiatives	0.763	12	Environmental Education in All Majors	0.831
6	Partnership for Resource-Saving Projects	0.813	13	Commitment to Green Practices	0.764
7	Courses on Sustainability	0.682	14	Support for Sustainable Research	0.744

The results of the last question in the survey asking students whether they consider their university to be a green university shown in Figure 1 revealed that a majority, 76%, responded "Yes," implying a positive perception of sustainability efforts on campus (Wiernik, et al., 2013). However, 24% of students answered "No," suggesting there is still room for progress in applying and communicating green initiatives (Filho, et al., 2016; Hassan, 2021c; Makuch & Aczel, 2020). This distribution reflects a strong foundation in sustainability and highlights the need for continued development to ensure that all students acknowledge and benefit from environmental efforts within their university (Alnaqbi et al., 2024; Azeiteiro & Davim, 2019; Begum et al., 2021; Citing Ardoin et al., 2020, Clery et al., 2021; Wu, 2021). Yet, while the results obtained from the survey reflect a strong foundation in sustainability, they also point out the necessity for continuous improvement to ensure that all students perceive their university as strongly committed to environmental responsibility. This can be achieved by addressing the concerns of 24% who remain uncertain that the university could further improve its position as a leader in sustainability and, in turn, create an environmentally aware student community.

Figure 1. Students' perspective on whether their university is green or not

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the critical success factors contributing to a green university considering students' perspectives at a university in Abu Dhabi United Arab Emirates. The research revealed that fourteen factors positively influence the sustainability initiative at universities as listed in Table 2. At this university, many students acknowledge the availability of effective sustainability initiatives such as sustainability-focused courses, recycle bins, and resources for disabled students. At the same time, 76% of students believe that the university widely pursues sustainability. However, there is room for advancement in communicating sustainability goals, increasing student engagement, and improving sustainability-related programs.

Despite the valuable insights in this study, it has limitations, including a smaller sample size than intended and the focus on a single university. These points have restricted generalizability. These limitations have also led to capturing student perceptions rather than professional insights and assessing only selected sustainability factors. In turn, this has potentially overlooked other key initiatives. Yet, the cross-sectional nature of this study has limited the long-term understanding of sustainability, as student perspectives may evolve. However, universities should improve student awareness and engagement while developing social inclusion programs, as they substantially contribute to sustainability insights (Alnaqbi et al., 2024; Clery et al., 2021). The research also adds to theoretical knowledge on sustainability assessment in higher education by identifying sustainability CSFs that influence student views and guiding universities in refining their sustainability strategies (Citing Ardoin et al., 2020; Hassan, 2021b; Keis, 2020). Nevertheless, universities should focus on raising awareness through sustainability education, hands-on workshops, and relevant events to advance sustainability efforts (Azeiteiro & Davim, 2019; Wu, 2021). Sustainability research should be supported to help students build problem-solving skills and confidence in tackling environmental challenges (Atici et al., 2021; Fuertes-Camacho et al., 2019; Hawkins, et al., 2023).

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